

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF STUDYING THE DEPENDENCE OF SANOGENIC THINKING ON PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS AND BEHAVIORAL STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents and the analysis of their individual-psychological aspects, the correlation values between the personality characteristics of the adolescents who participated in the study and questionnaires of Q-sort structure indicators, the comparison of the correlation values between personality characteristics and questionnaires of Q-sort structure indicators are presented in this article. analysis is covered.

Introduction. Creative, modular, reflexive technologies are put into practice as an important direction of improving the mechanisms of regulation of social and economic relations, increasing the social intelligence of a person, and developing sanogenic thinking, which contributes to the formation of spiritual and educational aspects. Improving cognitive, creative, socio-psychological mechanisms of interpersonal relations, kindness, patriotism, honesty, hard work, tolerance, loyalty, empathy, gratitude, developing philosophical-methodological, spiritual-ethical aspects of forming and developing healthy thinking, developing sanogenic thinking in young people systematic research on the development of expressive properties remains an urgent problem.

Literature review. The analysis of socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents and their individual-psychological aspects is considered one of the necessary issues to research thinking and the place of sanogenic thinking in the system of educational institutions of all developed countries today. In order to psychologically more fully illuminate sanogenic thinking in early adolescents, their individual-psychological capabilities, the ability to easily perform complex activities that occur within the framework of educational activities, the correct establishment of interpersonal relationships with teachers, the high level of emotional intelligence in

communication with the people around them, and the social-psychological factors several questionnaires that determine the emergence of psychological factors that develop the sanogenic thinking of students in determining the relationship between mutual psychological aspects, i.e. the "Level of Anxiety" method developed by Spielberger Khanin, the questionnaire "Study of the motive of success" by Ehlers, the "Sanogenic thinking" questionnaire by Morozyuk, the "Social Opinion" questionnaire and we used questionnaires such as "Q-sorting, i.e. determining personality behavior" developed by Stefanson. In the light of our research on sanogenic thinking in early adolescents, we looked at the overall indicators of students' sanogenic thinking, taking into account the regularities and characteristics between the psychological characteristics of sanogenic thinking. Their cross-poll correlations are presented below.

Results and discussion. Correlation values between questionnaires of personality characteristics and Q-sort structure indicators of adolescents who participated in the study are presented in the next table. (See Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators of correlation between personality traits and indicators of behavioral structure (according to K. Pearson's r-correlation coefficient)

Subordinate	Independent	0,373*
Independent	Adamovi	0,320*
Introductory	Anxiety	-0,329*
	Success motive	0,500**
Adamovi	Anxiety	-0,335*
	Sanogenic thinking	0,388*
A fighter	A fight avoider	-0,539**
	Sanogenic thinking	0,377*
A fight avoider	Success motive	0,343*
Anxiety	Success motive	0,905**
	Sanogenic thinking	0,709**
	Social thought	0,636**
Success motive	Sanogenic thinking	0,689**
	Social thought	0,606**
Sanogenic thinking	Social thought	0,923**

comment: * $p \leq 0,05$, ** $p \leq 0,01$.

The results obtained from the research on the psychological characteristics of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents show that the correlation between the factors of the questionnaires for the study of possibilities between the level of personality characteristics of high school students studying in public educational institutions and the indicators of Q-sort questionnaires are more dependent factors: independent ($r=0.373$, $r \leq 0.05$) with factors independent scale: personality ($r=0.320$, $r \leq 0.05$) with factors input scale: anxiety ($r=0.329$, $r \leq 0.05$) and success motive ($r=0.500$, $r \leq 0.01$) with the factors of the personality scale: anxiety ($r=0.335$, $r \leq 0.05$) and sanogenic thinking

($r=0.388$, $r \leq 0.05$), with the factors of the fighter scale: avoiding the fight ($r=0.539$, with the factors of $r \leq 0.01$) and sanogenic thinking ($r=0.377$, $r \leq 0.05$), the scale of struggle avoidance: achievement motive ($r=0.343$, $r \leq 0.01$) with the factors of the anxiety scale: achievement motive ($r = 0.905$, $r \leq 0.01$), with factors of sanogenic thinking ($r=0.709$, $r \leq 0.01$) and social opinion ($r=0.636$, $r \leq 0.01$), achievement motive scale: level of sanogenic thinking ($r= 0.689$, $r \leq 0.01$) and the level of social opinion ($r=0.606$, $r \leq 0.01$) and moderate correlations between factors such as sanogenic thinking scale: social opinion ($r=0.923$, $r \leq 0.01$) can be seen to exist. The next table shows the correlations of early adolescents' personality characteristics and Q-sort questionnaires. (See Table 2).

Indicators of correlation between personality traits and indicators of behavioral structure

(according to K. Pearson's r-correlation coefficient)

Subordinate	Introductory	0,328*
	A fighter	0,370*
Independent	Success motive	0,349*
Introductory	A fighter	0,353*
	Anxiety	-0,316*
	Sanogenic thinking	0,341*
	Social thought	0,364*
Adamovi	A fight avoider	0,381*
	Anxiety	0,385*
A fighter	Success motive	0,339*
	Sanogenic thinking	0,343*
A fight avoider	Social thought	0,366*
Anxiety	Success motive	-0,779**
	Sanogenic thinking	-0,772**
	Social thought	-0,675**
Success motive	Sanogenic thinking	0,778**
	Social thought	0,771**
Sanogenic thinking	Social thought	0,960**

comment: * $p \leq 0,05$, ** $p \leq 0,01$.

The results of questionnaires on the level of anxiety, success motive, social thinking, social opinion, and Q-sorting, which serve to develop sanogenic thinking in early adolescents, showed that the correlational relationships between the personality characteristics and personal behavior questionnaires of regional high school students more dependent scale: with factors of enterprising ($r=0.328$, $r \leq 0.05$) and struggling ($r=0.370$, $r \leq 0.05$), independent scale: with factors of achievement motive ($r=0.349$, $r \leq 0.05$) . , $r \leq 0.05$) with the factors Adamovi scale: struggle avoider ($r=0.381$, $r \leq 0.05$) and anxiety ($r=0.385$, $r \leq 0.05$) factors, the fighter scale: success motive ($r= 0.339$, $r \leq 0.05$) and sanogenic thinking ($r=0.343$, $r \leq 0.05$) with the factors of the avoidant scale: social thought ($r=0.366$, $r \leq 0.05$) with the factors of the anxiety scale: achievement motive

($r=0.779$, $r\leq 0.01$), success motive scale: Sanogenic thinking ($r=0.772$, $r\leq 0.01$) and social opinion ($r=0.675$, $r\leq 0.01$) factors. ($r=0.778$, $r\leq 0.01$) and with factors of social opinion ($r=0.771$, $r\leq 0.01$), to see that the scale of sanogenic thinking: social opinion ($r=0.960$, $r\leq 0.01$) was highly correlated possible The following table shows the correlations between the level of personality characteristics of early adolescents and the Q-sort questionnaire. (See Table 3).

Table 3

Indicators of correlation between personality traits and indicators of behavioral structure

(according to K. Pearson's r-correlation coefficient)

Subordinate	Independent	0,324*
	A fight avoider	0,389*
Independent	A fighter	0,318*
Introductory	A fight avoider	0,369*
	Success motive	0,360*
Adamovi	A fight avoider	-0,345*
A fighter	Anxiety	0,406**
	Success motive	-0,378*
A fight avoider	Anxiety	0,321*
Anxiety	Success motive	-0,818**
	Sanogenic thinking	-0,699**
	Social thought	-0,695**
Success motive	Sanogenic thinking	0,767**
	Social thought	0,716**
Sanogenic thinking	Social thought	0,936**

comment: * $p\leq 0,05$, ** $p\leq 0,01$.

The results of the study on the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents show that the correlation between the factors on the questionnaires for the study of the possibilities between the level of personality characteristics and indicators of personality behavior is more dependent factors: independent ($r=0.324$, $r\leq 0.05$) and with the factors of struggle-avoidance ($r=0.389$, $r\leq 0.05$), independent scale: struggle ($r=0.318$, $r\leq 0.05$) with factors, input scale: struggle-avoidance ($r=0.369$, $r\leq 0.05$)) and achievement motive ($r=0.360$, $r\leq 0.05$) factors, with the personality scale: struggle avoider ($r=0.345$, $r\leq 0.05$) factors, the fighter scale: anxiety ($r=0.406$, $r\leq 0.05$) 01) and success motive ($r=0.378$, $r\leq 0.05$) with the factors of the avoidant struggle scale: anxiety ($r=0.321$, $r\leq 0.05$) with the factors of the anxiety scale: success motive ($r=0.818$, $r\leq 0.01$), with the factors of sanogenic thinking ($r=0.699$, $r\leq 0.01$) and social opinion ($r=0.695$, $r\leq 0.01$), success motive scale: sanogenic thinking ($r=0.767$, $r\leq 0, 01$) and social opinion ($r=0.716$, $r\leq 0.01$) factors, it can be seen that the scale of sanogenic thinking: social opinion ($r=0.936$, $r\leq 0.01$) is highly correlated. The next table shows the structural models of early adolescent personality traits and Q-sort questionnaires. (See Table 4).

Table 4

A structural model of indicators of personality traits and behavioral structure

Scales	Ljung-Box Q (18)		
	Statistical indicators (M-1)	Statistical indicators (M-2)	Statistical indicators (M-3)
worry	13,06	20,29	29,86
success motive	23,59	11,82	24,38
sanogenic thinking	25,74	10,03	12,25
social thought	12,24	9,41	18,28
subordinate	24,59	31,03	21,63
independent	9,40	18,83	32,42
accessible	24,58	20,62	8,13
man	26,82	19,34	34,21
fighter	19,29	39,18	10,83
avoiding the struggle	15,73	24	10,06

In order to strengthen the practical aspects of the scientific research conducted on the socio-psychological features of the development of Sanogenic thinking, the questionnaires conducted in early adolescents provided an opportunity to determine the higher or lower scales according to the structural model. According to regions, the higher structural units expressed by students of rural schools in the questionnaires: units such as success motive, sanogenic thinking, subordination, enterprising and sociable, and the lower scales: psychological structural units such as anxiety, social opinion, independent, fighting and avoiding struggle, City school high psychological units in high school students: anxiety, subordination, introspective, combative and avoidant units, and the lower level psychological characteristics such as success motive, sanogenic thinking, social thinking, independent and sociable, high psychological units in early adolescents studying in urban schools: anxiety, success motive, dependent, independent and humanistic scales, and the overall result can be seen to reflect psychological structural models such as synogenic thinking, social thinking, enterprising, combative and avoidant.

Conclusions. In this chapter, dedicated to the results of the empirical study of the influence of Sanogenic thinking on the social behavior of students, we came to the following conclusions:

1. The psychological factors of the level of development of sanogenic thinking in students show that they have a high ratio of several characteristics, i.e. success motive, level of sanogenic thinking, social opinion, dependence, independent, enterprising and fighting scales, on the contrary, psychological factors such as anxiety level, shyness and avoidance of struggle are negative. shown to be showing the value.

2. Taking into account the characteristics related to the research work on the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in high school students, the indicators of the scales in the questionnaire according to the factor analysis: anxiety, success motive, the level of sanogenic thinking, social opinion, independent and enterprising psychological factors show a high weight, subordinate, sociable, combative and avoidant scales were found to show lower factors.

3. In early adolescents, sanogenic thinking creates motivation for the optimal level of cognitive processes and the formation of positive mental abilities.

Personal qualities such as stress tolerance, lack of nervousness, social and psychological flexibility, easy access to interpersonal relationships, ability to control the emotional sphere are highly invisible in people with developed sanogenic thinking.

4. The main reasons for the need to increase attention to healthy thinking of early adolescents: as a result of the development of science and technology, culture, art and literature, socio-economic conditions are changing; due to the expansion of mass media, the level of awareness of teenagers has increased; accelerated physical and mental development of early adolescents; the need for a special approach to ideological-political, patriotic and international education when working with early adolescents;

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